

SOCIALIZATION AND GUIDANCE IN THE MAKING OF HERBAL SAUNAS IN ALUE DEAH TEUNGOH VILLAGE IN 2025

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Abstract

The International Labor Organization (ILO) reports that 2 million people die in the workplace, one of the causes being overexertion. Herbal saunas are decoctions of plants with medicinal properties, including anti-fatigue. Warm steam applied to the skin helps dilate blood vessels, improving circulation. The purpose of this activity was to provide knowledge about various medicinal plants that can be used as herbal saunas and to provide community members with skills in making herbal saunas. The PKM method involved participation through outreach and mentoring women in preparing herbal saunas. The activity took place on July 27, 2025, in Alue Deah Teungoh Village, with 15 women participating in the Family Welfare Movement (PKK). The activity began with a pre-test and then a herbal sauna booklet. The results of this activity were an increase in the knowledge and skills of the PKK women, demonstrated by the resulting product, a dried herbal sauna packaged in a standing pouch. Participants were very enthusiastic about the training. The activity concluded with the use of herbal saunas, which were boiled in a steamer and the steam flowed into a portable sauna tent. Participants took turns using the sauna, which had been filled with the herbal sauna decoction.

Keywords: *herbal sauna, socialization, mentoring. PKK women.*

INTRODUCTION

The topic of complementary therapies has become increasingly relevant in many countries. Complementary therapies combine traditional practices with contemporary medical approaches. There is growing interest in complementary or traditional therapies among the Indonesian population. This growing interest is reflected in the increasing number of people visiting complementary therapy centers in various locations. The types of therapies included in complementary therapies vary, which is why they are often referred to as holistic therapies. The term holistic health relates to a holistic integration that influences health, encourages positive behavior, provides a sense of purpose, and supports spiritual growth (Hitchcock et al., 1999). One form of complementary therapy is herbal sauna. Sauna is an ancestral practice of the Indonesian people that aims to cleanse skin impurities. This herbal sauna can be enjoyed in two ways: by soaking in warm water with herbal spices or through an herbal steam sauna using various herbs (Harini, 2024).

Herbal saunas are plant decoctions that produce aromas known as aromatherapy. The fragrant compounds found in the essential oils of various plants can refresh the skin and boost metabolism. Warm steam on contact with the skin helps dilate blood vessels, improving circulation. Sweating during a herbal bath is part of the detoxification process, helping to remove toxins from the body. Benefits of herbal saunas include weight loss, relieving aches and pains, treating insomnia, detoxifying the body, and reducing fatigue (Khadijah, 2024). Santi's (2023) research on the living pharmacy in the Gampong Alue Deah Teungoh area revealed a variety of medicinal plants. However, the low utilization of herbal plants for therapy, disease prevention, and treatment has resulted in these local treasures being used only as complementary spices for food. Therefore, the upcoming community service (PKM) activities play a crucial role in increasing the knowledge and skills of women in processing herbal plants into nutritious spices

packaged as herbal saunas. In order to improve the knowledge and skills of the Deah Teungoh Village community, it is very important to carry out socialization and mentoring activities for making herbal saunas.

METHOD

The activity method used was active participation, including outreach and mentoring for women in Alue Deah Teungoh Village in making herbal saunas. This community service included presentations on herbal saunas, the herbal compositions used, their benefits, and techniques for making them. The materials were packaged in a booklet and provided time for a question-and-answer session. The next activity involved practical herbal sauna making by the women, assisted by the community service team. The community service activity will be held on July 25, 2025, at the PKK Office in Alue Deah Teungoh Village. Preparations for the PKM activity will last for three months, from May 10 to August 10, 2025.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The activity began with a pre-test distributed to participants, followed by booklets. Participants included 15 PKK leaders and women from the Alue Deah Teungoh Village PKK committee. The booklets were attractively packaged and included souvenirs as a token of appreciation for their attendance. The team observed the participants' enthusiasm and eagerness to participate, as demonstrated by their focused attention to the material presented by the PkM team. The team explained herbal saunas, their benefits, and herbs with medicinal properties, particularly anti-fatigue properties. The women listened attentively to the presenters' presentations on processing plants for herbal saunas and blending them into products. The next activity involved a question-and-answer session or discussion on any unclear material. The presenters posed questions to test participants' understanding of the material. Door prizes were awarded as a token of appreciation for their willingness and active participation. Based on the community service team's outreach, the majority of participants were able to answer questions effectively. This demonstrates that the information conveyed by the presenters was well received and understood (Candra, 2022). The team also encouraged participants to cultivate their own herbs from their yards into herbal saunas, which have health-boosting benefits. The activity concluded with a post-test. T-test analysis revealed an increase in knowledge before and after the PKM.

Figure 1. The service team provides health education

For Indonesians, most health problems are addressed through traditional methods, one of which is the use of plants. Some plants are believed to prevent, cure, and even eliminate diseases in the body. Some plants are believed to maintain health, beauty, and increase stamina. The use of plants for medicinal purposes is not limited to direct consumption (drinking and eating) but also implicitly, such as through processing and steaming (Biofarmaka IPB 2013). The use of plants (herbs) as therapy can be done through a steaming process (sauna). The term sauna can refer to any building or facility that includes a steam bath. A sauna is a room characterized by high temperature and low humidity, used to encourage the body to sweat and burn additional calories. In general, infrared saunas operate at lower temperatures than conventional saunas. The internal temperature of a sauna can reach up to 90.5°C, which can raise the skin temperature to around 40°C in just a few minutes. Due to the high heat, saunas induce sweating, dilate blood vessels, improve blood circulation, and promote relaxation (Apriyani, 2022). Saunas serve as an effective

means of relaxation that can benefit heart health. Typically, there are two main types of saunas: conventional saunas and infrared saunas. Conventional saunas use space heaters to warm the air, while infrared saunas use light energy to raise body temperature without significantly increasing the air temperature. (Maharani, 2009).

Herbs, commonly called spices, are a type of plant often used as natural flavorings or preservatives in culinary dishes. The primary benefits of spices include enhancing the flavor of food and providing warmth to the body. Spices can be further categorized into several groups, including medicinal plants, aromatic vegetables, and dried fruits (Purnawan, 2015). There are several benefits of herbal saunas, including:

- a). Body detoxification refers to the process of eliminating toxins from the body, one effective method of which is through sweating. Sweating significantly can efficiently eliminate toxins absorbed through various means. One healthy way to induce sweating is to enjoy a steam bath in an herbal sauna. The warm sauna environment encourages the body to expel toxins through excessive sweating caused by the hot steam.
- b). Helps boost immunity. Steam baths can stimulate the production of white blood cells, which are crucial in protecting the body from various pathogens, such as bacteria and viruses, that cause disease. Regular sauna users are believed to have higher white blood cell levels than those who don't, helping them maintain health and recover more quickly from illness.
- c). Helps with weight loss. The dry heat during a steam bath can significantly increase the heart rate. Research supports that a 20-minute steam bath at 170°F (approximately 75°C) can help burn over 500 calories. Furthermore, the body's metabolism during a steam bath can increase similarly to physical exercise.
- d). Helps relax muscles and joints. Steam baths are thought to reduce the risk of arthritis, fibromyalgia, or stress. Furthermore, they are considered an effective and natural solution for rapid relief from muscle pain.
- e). Helps improve sleep quality. The hot steam used in a bath can have a calming effect, making the body and mind feel more at ease, thus improving sleep quality.
- f). Helps relieve stress. Steam baths can increase blood circulation and trigger the release of endorphins, leading to a more relaxed state in the body and mind, thereby reducing stress levels.

The herbs used in herbal saunas have diverse properties, so the overall therapeutic effect of the herbs leaves the body healthy and refreshed. The composition of herbal saunas is as follows:

- a. Red ginger helps regenerate dead skin cells, which can help prevent signs of premature aging. Furthermore, ginger can cleanse impurities from the skin. Furthermore, ginger promotes calm and relaxation. Ginger contains antioxidants that can prevent cancer and improve stomach health. Furthermore, ginger can soothe the respiratory tract, relieve coughs, and treat nausea and vomiting (Ade, 2014).
- b. Red betel leaves contain various chemical components, such as flavonoids and polyphenols, which function as antioxidants, antidiabetic, anticancer, antiseptic, and anti-inflammatory agents. Furthermore, the alkaloid compounds found in red betel can act as inhibitors of cancer cell growth (Gunawan, 2004).
- c. Pandanus leaves contain antioxidants that can prevent cancer and improve stomach health. Furthermore, pandan leaves can soothe the respiratory tract, relieve coughs, and treat nausea and vomiting (Noorhamdani, 2010).
- d. Nutmeg acts as an antioxidant, antimicrobial, antifungal, and preservative. Nutmeg is effective in reducing acne scars and can also be used to treat acne. Furthermore, nutmeg has natural anti-inflammatory properties (Adiani, 2013).
- e. Lemongrass is a traditional medicine used to treat sore throats, colitis, gastritis, diarrhea, as a mouthwash, and stomach aches. Traditionally, lemongrass can be used as a liniment, to treat skin inflammation, as a bathwater mixture for those suffering from illness, as a cleansing agent, to relieve headaches, and to treat insect bites, coughs, and colds. (Kurniawati, 2010).
- f. Cloves are used as a conventional medicine because they have properties for treating toothaches, menstrual problems, aches, wounds and torture, colds, as a warming agent, and to soothe nausea (Nuraini, 2014).
- g. Turmeric functions to exfoliate dead skin cells. It can smooth rough skin and also helps maintain skin hydration. The result is clear, acne-free, and brighter-looking skin. Turmeric has benefits for various ailments, including antioxidant, antitumor, and anticancer effects, anti-aging, reducing fat and cholesterol levels in the blood and liver, as well as antimicrobial, antiseptic, and anti-inflammatory properties (Hartati, 2013).
- h. Cinnamon is effective in treating acne. It can cleanse the skin and improve its radiance. A scrub made with cinnamon is especially beneficial for those with dry skin. Another benefit is its ability to remove dead skin cells. Cinnamon is also effective in treating conditions such as gout, hypertension, ulcers, loss of appetite, headaches, diarrhea, gas, vomiting, hernias, constipation, asthma, mouth ulcers, and diabetes mellitus (Prapti, 2013).
- i. Bay leaves are beneficial for the body because they contain minerals such as potassium, calcium, copper, magnesium, manganese, zinc, amino acids, and selenium. Bay leaves are used to treat cholesterol, prevent diabetes, heal stomach ulcers, improve digestion, and lower high blood pressure (Made, 2021).

CLOSING

Conclusion

The community service activities included distributing booklets and providing information using PowerPoint. This was followed by a discussion and Q&A session related to the material provided by the community service team. These activities helped build participants' awareness and understanding of herbal plants, which can be used to prevent fatigue and other ailments. Participants appeared enthusiastic and engaged in the series of activities. Follow-up action included coordination with the village head of Atong Village to ensure the continuous production of the formulated products to improve the community's economy.

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